

THE INFLUENCE OF THE META-ARAMID/EPOXY NANOFIBER MATS ON THE ADHESION STRENGTH AT CRYOGENIC ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The reliability of adhesive joining structures in cryogenic environment is affected by thermal residual stress induced by difference of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between adherends and adhesive. Therefore, the adhesive layer requires reinforcing materials that has low CTEs to relieve the mismatch of thermal expansion with adherends for the reliability of cryogenic structure. In this work, meta-aramid nanofiber mats which have high specific strength and low CTE were used to reinforce the adhesive. Electrospun core-shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofibers were fabricated by polymer blend method to reform the inert surface of the meta-aramid through the in-situ surface treatment. The effect of the reinforcement on reducing thermal residual stress in cryogenic environment was investigated by performing single-lap joints test under -150°C . The residual strain distribution of room temperature and cryogenic temperature was measured by using Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor with Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry (OFDR) systems. Finite Element Analysis was also performed to compare with experimental data. As a result, core-shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofiber mats were effectively reduced residual stress in adhesive layer on cryogenic environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesive joining structures are widely used in cryogenic environment such as Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) ships and sealing parts of cryogenic containment system. The strength of the adhesive joints at the cryogenic temperatures is influenced by the property variation of adhesive and the thermal residual stress generated due to the large temperature difference (ΔT) from the adhesive bonding process to the operating temperature [1]. Thermal residual stresses have an important role in failure of the adhesive joint [2]. Therefore, the adhesive layer requires reinforcing materials that has low CTEs to relieve the mismatch of thermal expansion with adherends for the reliability of cryogenic structure. Timmerman et al. showed the effect of nano-clay reinforcement in carbon fiber/epoxy composite to enhance the resistance of cyclical thermal stress at cryogenic temperature [3]. Kim et al. investigated the effect of randomly oriented aramid fiber mats to reduce thermal residual stress and to improve fracture toughness of adhesively joint at cryogenic environments [4].

Aramid fibers can be used to reduce the CTE and increase the bonding strength in adhesive of adhesively joining structures because they have high strength, good fracture toughness, excellent thermal resistance, and low density compared to inorganic fibers such as glass and carbon [5]. Additionally, CTE ($15.0 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) of commercial meta-aramid fibers is lower than that of adhesives ($50\text{--}100 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) [6]. However, the employing aramid fiber as reinforcement has been limited by poor fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion because the fiber surface has insufficient reactive functional groups for bonding with the matrix resin [7-8]. Thus many researchers have been investigated surface treatment methods for aramid fibers such as chemical treatment, plasma treatment and mechanical abrasion. The conventional surface treatment methods, however, has negative effects on the mechanical properties of aramid fibers.

Core/shell nanofibers can be electrospun directly from the polymer blends by controlling the phase separation [9]. Different molecular weights of the polymer were critical to the formation of core sheath structures because the higher viscosity materials located in the center of the nanofiber and the lower viscosity material located in the sheath due to rheological effects [10]. Core/shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofiber can achieve a substantial increase in the wettability, toughness, and mechanical properties of the adhesive at cryogenic temperature of -150°C .

In this work, the epoxy adhesive was reinforced by electrospun core-shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofiber mats for reducing residual stress at cryogenic temperature. Single lap joint tests were performed and the residual strain was measured by using Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor with Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry (OFDR) systems. Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed to calculate the strain and stress distribution in adhesive layer. Finally, the effects of nanofiber mats on reducing residual stress at the cryogenic environments were investigated through the FEA results.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Electrospinning of meta-aramid nanofibers

Meta-aramid was synthesized using an equal molar ratio of m-phenylene diamine (P23954, Sigma–Aldrich, USA) and 1,3-isophthaloyl chloride (I19403, Sigma–Aldrich, USA) in DMAc (Samchun Inc., Korea) [11]. The average molecular weight of the polymer was $381,000\text{g/mol}$ (DMAc, GPC). The meta-aramid solution was also blended with Bisphenol-A and F mixed type epoxy resin (Araldite AW106, Huntsman, UK) to fabricate the core/shell structure.

A pristine meta-aramid solution was dissolved in DMAc at 80°C to prepare solutions at 12 wt.%. Meta-aramid solution was blended with epoxy resin as 9:1 (Meta-aramid/Epoxy) ratio. An electrospinning process was performed at voltage of 15 kV with a distance of 10 cm between the collector and the tip of the syringe. The fabricated nanofiber mats were dried for 24 h in a vacuum to remove any residual solvent.

2.2 Thermo-Mechanical Analysis (TMA) Test

Thermo-mechanical analysis (TMA) was used to characterize the CTE of the adhesive composite materials. The CTE of the epoxy adhesives reinforced with the meta-aramid nanofiber mats was obtained by measuring the dimensional change of the specimens with respect to temperature. Each specimen was gradually heated ($3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) from -100 to 0°C , and the corresponding dimensional change was recorded using a TMA 2940 analyzer (TA Instrument, USA). The results were calculated based on the mean slopes of the curves and are listed in Table 1.

2.3 Single Lap Joint Tests

The configuration of single lap joint was presented in Figure 1. The single lap joint specimens were composed of $20 \times 100 \times 3$ (width x length x thickness)mm sized S45C steel as adherends, Bisphenol-A and F mixed type epoxy resin (Araldite AW106, Huntsman, UK) with a polyamide curing agent (Araldite 953, Huntsman, UK) as Adhesive. The area of adhesive was 10×20 mm. and the thickness of the adhesive layer was maintained at 0.3 mm by using thickness gage. The nanofiber mats of reinforcements in the single lap joint test were cut into pieces with dimensions of $20 \times 10 \times 0.06$ mm.

The nanofiber mats were carefully placed in the specimens, after which epoxy paste adhesive was applied to the specimens to impregnate the nanofiber mats. Epoxy resin was cured at 80 °C during 120 -min. The lap shear strength of the meta-aramid/epoxy adhesive joints was measured using a computer-controlled material testing system (4206, INSTRON, USA) [12]. The tests were conducted with a loading speed of 1.0 mm/min at 25 °C and -150 °C.

Figure 1: Configuration of Single lap joint specimens

2.4 Monitoring of Cure Process with OFDR (Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry)

The distributed sensing system consists of a tunable laser source (TLS), a PD, a broadband reflector (R), a 3 dB coupler (C), long-length FBGs (FBG_{α} , $\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, N$) whose gauge length is about 100 mm and a computer (PC) with a high-speed A/D converter (DAQ) [13]. Signal processing technique based on short time Fourier transform (STFT) to map the strain profile along FBGs. Finally strain distribution along the FBGs is determined by the distribution of center wavelength shift between the initial condition and the current one [14]. Schematic diagram of FBG with OFDR systems were shown as Figure 2.

A FBG sensor was embedded into the bottom side of adhesive layer. The variation of strain distribution during cure process and after curing process was measured by using the FBG sensor with OFDR systems. The strain was measured at an interval of 30 min in the curing process.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of FBG sensor with OFDR system

Figure 3: Monitoring of cure process. (a) Neat Epoxy adhesive and (b) Nanofiber toughened epoxy adhesive.

Strain monitoring results during cure process and after the cure process were shown in Figure 3. Basically, the wavelength was increased as the curing time increased. After the curing process, the wavelength was decreased as the temperature decreased. The sensor was shrunk as the specimens were cooled down rapidly. This effect induced a contraction on the FBG sensor embedded into the center of the adhesive layer, which resulted in a negative evolution of strain.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS (FEA)

Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed to verify for the effect of core-shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofiber mats on reducing residual strain and stress at cryogenic environments. The strain and stress distribution was also investigated during the curing process and lap shear test at room temperature and cryogenic temperature.

Figure 4: Modeling of the single lap joint for FE Analysis

3.1 Finite Element modeling of the single-lap joint

	<i>Elastic modulus</i> E (GPa)	<i>Shear modulus</i> G (GPa)	<i>Poisson's ratio</i>	<i>Coefficient of thermal expansion</i> ($\mu/^\circ\text{C}$)
<i>Araldite (25 °C)</i>	1.5	0.52	0.43	54
<i>Araldite (-150 °C)</i>	5.6	1.96	0.43	31
<i>Steel</i>	193	-	0.3	14
<i>Nanofiber toughened epoxy</i>	$E_1 = 1.97$	$G_{12} = 0.52$	$\nu_{12} = 0.44$	48.6
	$E_2 = 1.78$	$G_{13} = 0.52$	$\nu_{13} = 0.44$	
	$E_2 = 1.78$	$G_{23} = 0.52$	$\nu_{23} = 0.43$	

Table 1: Mechanical properties of epoxy adhesive and nanofiber toughened epoxy.

The strain and stress distribution in adhesive layer was calculated by a commercial finite element analysis software using ABAQUS 6.13 (ABAQUS Inc., RI, USA). Figure 4 shows the finite element modelling and boundary conditions. Tap parts on edge of the adhereends and thickness gages for controlling adhesive thickness were neglected in our FEA model. The right end of upper adherend was applied to displacement constraint and left end of lower adherend was applied to tensile load. Using the material properties was shown in Table 1. C3D8 type elements (8-node brick element) were used and total number of elements was 274,260. Also, nonlinear geometry and nonlinear material properties were considered. The FEA was performed from the curing process to single lap joint test

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5: Residual strain distribution obtained by experiments and FEA (a) Neat epoxy adhesive joint at room temperature and (b) Nanofiber toughened epoxy adhesive joint

Figure 5 shows the residual strain distribution obtained by experiments and FEA. In case of neat epoxy adhesive joint, residual strain in the adhesive longitudinal directions (E_{11}) generated by difference in curing temperature and room temperature. Both case of (a) and (b) shows the similar tendency in middle range of adhesive layer (0.1 ~ 0.9 range of normalized distance) between experiment result and FEA result. However, strain values of adhesive edge part (0 ~ 0.1 and 0.9 ~ 1 range of normalized distance) showed different tendency. All case of experiment data (a) and (b) was obtained to tensile strain value, whereas FEA result was shown compressive strain value, because the residue of epoxy resin was remained on the edge of FBG sensor and adherends.

Figure 6: Stress distribution as FEA result of neat epoxy and nanofiber toughened epoxy adhesive layer (a) S_{11} at room temperature, (b) S_{22} at room temperature, (c) S_{11} at cryogenic temperature and (d) S_{22} at cryogenic temperature

	<i>Left edge</i> <i>Maximum stress (MPa)</i>	<i>Right edge</i> <i>Maximum stress (MPa)</i>
<i>(a), Neat epoxy</i>	34.543	50.650
<i>Nanofiber toughened epoxy</i>	24.705	31.011
<i>(b), Neat epoxy</i>	33.152	74.099
<i>Nanofiber toughened epoxy</i>	23.180	47.36
<i>(c), Neat epoxy</i>	60.166	68.668
<i>Nanofiber toughened epoxy</i>	42.166	45.455
<i>(d), Neat epoxy</i>	26.792	56.680
<i>Nanofiber toughened epoxy</i>	19.445	36.320

Table 2: Maximum stress value at left edge and right edge in single lap joints.

Figure 6. shows the stress distribution during tensile loading of neat epoxy joint and nanofiber toughened epoxy adhesive joint at room temperature and cryogenic temperature. Figure 6 (a) and (b) presented S_{11} , longitudinal stress in adhesive layer at room temperatures and cryogenic temperature, respectively. Figure 6 (c) and (b) presented S_{22} , stress in the thickness direction in adhesive layer at room temperatures and cryogenic temperature, respectively. The maximum stress value occurred in left edge (0 ~ 0.1 range of normalized distance) and right edge (0.9 ~ 1 range of normalized distance). Maximum stress level was decreased as the meta-aramide/epoxy nanofiber mats are reinforced in adhesive layer as shown in Table 2.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, effects of core-shell structured meta-aramid/epoxy nanofiber mats on reducing residual stress at cryogenic environments were investigated by using embedded FBG sensor with OFDR systems and finite element analysis. Based on the results, the following conclusions were obtained.

1. The strain distributions were successfully measured during cure process and single lap joint tests.
2. FEA result of thermal residual strain at room temperature was well matched with experiment result.
3. The maximum longitudinal stress (S_{11}) and stress in the thickness direction (S_{22}) was decreased about more than 50% when the meta-aramide/epoxy nanofiber mats are reinforced in adhesive layer at the room temperature and cryogenic temperature.

From the results, it was found that core-shell structured meta-aramide/epoxy nanofiber mats are promising materials to reduce the thermal residual stress and strain of the single lap joints at room temperature and cryogenic temperature

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